

Versioned Archive and Review of Biotic
Interactions and Taxon Names Found within
millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-
portal-for-fish-stomach-records
hash://md5/ac764358b1c7a47d82d5c560aee719e5

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Abstract

Life on Earth is sustained by complex interactions between organisms and their environment. These biotic interactions can be captured in datasets and published digitally. We present a review and archiving process for such an openly accessible digital interactions dataset of known origin and discuss its outcome. The dataset under review, named millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records, has fingerprint hash://md5/ac764358b1c7a47d82d5c560aee719e5, is 32.6MiB in size and contains 225,564 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 187 primary taxa (e.g., GADUS MORHUA) and 1,268 associated taxa (e.g., EMPTY). This report includes detailed summaries of interaction data, a taxonomic review from multiple catalogs, and an archived version of the dataset from which the reviews are derived.

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Introduction

Data Review and Archive

Data review and archiving can be a time-consuming process, especially when done manually. This review report aims to help facilitate both activities. It automates the archiving of datasets, including Darwin Core archives, and is a citable backup of a version of the dataset. Additionally, an automatic review of species interaction claims made in the dataset is generated and registered with Global Biotic Interactions (J. H. Poelen, Simons, and Mungall 2014).

This review includes summary statistics about, and observations about, the dataset under review :

Pinnegar, J.K. (2014). DAPSTOM - An Integrated Database & Portal for Fish Stomach Records. Version 4.7. Centre for Environment, Fisheries & Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK. February 2014, 39pp. <https://zenodo.org/records/258222/files/millierse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records-v1.0.zip>
2026-06-06T14:58:22.339Z hash://md5/ac764358b1c7a47d82d5c560aee719e5

Methods

The review is performed through programmatic scripts that leverage tools like Preston (Elliott et al. 2025), Elton (Kuhn, Poelen, and Leinweber 2025), Nomer (Salim and Poelen 2025), globinizer (J. Poelen, Seltmann, and Mietchen 2024) combined with third-party tools like grep, mlr, tail and head.

Table 1: Tools used in this review process

tool name	version
preston	0.11.1
elton	0.16.11
nomer	0.6.5
globinizer	0.4.0
mlr	6.0.0
jq	1.6
yq	4.25.3
pandoc	3.1.6.1
duckdb	1.3.1
mapserver	7.6.4

The review process can be described in the form of the script below ¹.

```
# get versioned copy of the dataset (size approx. 32.6MiB) under review
elton pull millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records

# generate review notes
elton review millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records \
> review.tsv

# export indexed interaction records
elton interactions millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records \
> interactions.tsv

# export names and align them with the Catalogue of Life using Nomer
elton names millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records \
| nomer append col \
> name-alignment.tsv
```

or visually, in a process diagram.

You can find a copy of the full review script at [check-data.sh](#). See also [GitHub](#) and [Codeberg](#).

¹Note that you have to first get the data (e.g., via `elton pull millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records`) before being able to generate reviews (e.g., `elton review millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records`), extract interaction claims (e.g., `elton interactions millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records`), or list taxonomic names (e.g., `elton names millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records`)

Figure 1: Review Process Overview

Results

In the following sections, the results of the review are summarized ². Then, links to the detailed review reports are provided.

Files

An extensive list of files produced as part of the review process can be found in Appendix A. Review Files.

Archived Dataset

Note that *data.zip* file in this archive contains the complete, unmodified archived dataset under review.

Biotic Interactions

Figure 2: Biotic Interaction Data Model

In this review, biotic interactions (or biotic associations) are modeled as a primary (aka subject, source) organism interacting with an associate (aka object, target) organism. The dataset under review classified the primary/associate organisms with specific taxa. The primary and associate organisms The kind of interaction is documented as an interaction type.

The dataset under review, named millerse/Dapstrom-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records, has fingerprint hash://md5/ac764358b1c7a47d82d5c560aee719e5,

²Disclaimer: The results in this review should be considered friendly, yet naive, notes from an unsophisticated robot. Please keep that in mind when considering the review results.

is 32.6MiB in size and contains 225,564 interactions with 1 unique type of association (e.g., eats) between 187 primary taxa (e.g., GADUS MORHUA) and 1,268 associated taxa (e.g., EMPTY).

An exhaustive list of indexed interaction claims can be found in gzipped csv, tsv, geopackage and parquet archives. To facilitate discovery, a preview of claims available in the gzipped html page at [indexed-interactions.html.gz](#) are shown below.

The exhaustive list was used to create the following data summaries below.

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
-----------------	---------------------	-----------------	-------------------

Table 2: Sample of Indexed Interaction Claims

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SCOMBER SCOMBRUS	eats	ACARTIA CLAUSI	Pinnegar, J.K. (2014). DAPSTOM - An Integrated Database & Portal for Fish Stomach Records. Version 4.7. Centre for Environment, Fisheries & Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK. February 2014, 39pp. Accessed at https://www.cefas.co.uk/umbraco/CefasPlugins/DapstomSurface/Download?searchType=predator&species=MAC&years=2011&years=2010&years=2006&years=2005&years=2004&years=1991&years=1987&years=1986&years=1979&years=1978&years=1977&years=1976&years=1974&years=1972&years=1965&years=1956&years=1919&years=1917&years=1907&years=1906&years=1902&years=1901&years=1899&areas=VIIIb&areas=VIIa&areas=VIa&areas=VIIIc&areas=XIVb&areas=VIIg&areas=VIIIh&areas=VIIa&areas=IIa&areas=XIVa&areas=VIIId

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeNam	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SCOMBER SCOMBRUS	eats	ACARTIA CLAUSI	Pinnegar, J.K. (2014). DAPSTOM - An Integrated Database & Portal for Fish Stomach Records. Version 4.7. Centre for Environment, Fisheries & Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK. February 2014, 39pp. Accessed at https://www.cefas.co.uk/umbraco/CefasPlugins/DapstomSurface/Download?searchType=predator&species=MAC&years=2011&years=2010&years=2006&years=2005&years=2004&years=1991&years=1987&years=1986&years=1979&years=1978&years=1977&years=1976&years=1974&years=1972&years=1965&years=1956&years=1919&years=1917&years=1907&years=1906&years=1902&years=1901&years=1899&areas=VIIIb&areas=VIa&areas=VIIj&areas=VIa&areas=VIIIc&areas=XIVb&areas=VIIg&areas=VIIh&areas=VIIa&areas=IIa&areas=XIVa&areas=VIIId&areas=VIIe&areas=VIIf&areas=IVa&areas=I

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeNam	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SCOMBER SCOMBRUS	eats	ACARTIA CLAUSI	Pinnegar, J.K. (2014). DAPSTOM - An Integrated Database & Portal for Fish Stomach Records. Version 4.7. Centre for Environment, Fisheries & Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK. February 2014, 39pp. Accessed at https://www.cefas.co.uk/umbraco/CefasPlugins/DapstomSurface/Download?searchType=predator&species=MAC&years=2011&years=2010&years=2006&years=2005&years=2004&years=1991&years=1987&years=1986&years=1979&years=1978&years=1977&years=1976&years=1974&years=1972&years=1965&years=1956&years=1919&years=1917&years=1907&years=1906&years=1902&years=1901&years=1899&areas=VIIIb&areas=VIa&areas=VIIj&areas=VIIc&areas=XIVb&areas=VIIg&areas=VIIh&areas=VIIa&areas=IIa&areas=XIVa&areas=IIId&areas=VIIe&areas=VIIf&areas=IVa&areas=I

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeNam	targetTaxonName	referenceCitation
SCOMBER SCOMBRUS	eats	ACARTIA CLAUSI	Pinnegar, J.K. (2014). DAPSTOM - An Integrated Database & Portal for Fish Stomach Records. Version 4.7. Centre for Environment, Fisheries & Aquaculture Science, Lowestoft, UK. February 2014, 39pp. Accessed at https://www.cefas.co.uk/umbraco/CefasPlugins/DapstomSurface/Download?searchType=predator&species=MAC&years=2011&years=2010&years=2006&years=2005&years=2004&years=1991&years=1987&years=1986&years=1979&years=1978&years=1977&years=1976&years=1974&years=1972&years=1965&years=1956&years=1919&years=1917&years=1907&years=1906&years=1902&years=1901&years=1899&areas=VIIIb&areas=VIa&areas=VIIj&areas=VIa&areas=VIIIc&areas=XIVb&areas=VIIg&areas=VIIh&areas=VIIa&areas=IIa&areas=XIVa&areas=VIIId&areas=VIIe&areas=VIIf&areas=IVa&areas=I

Table 3: Most Frequently Mentioned Interaction Types (up to 20 most frequent)

interactionTypeName	count
eats	225564

Table 4: Most Frequently Mentioned Primary Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	count
GADUS MORHUA	67884
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	47017
MELANOGRAMMUS AEGLEFINUS	19823
PLEURONECTES PLATESSA	12916
SCOMBER SCOMBRUS	10489
CLUPEA HARENGUS	8508
EUTRIGLA GURNARDUS	8327
LIMANDA LIMANDA	4837
SPRATTUS SPRATTUS	4651
LEPIDORHOMBUS WHIFFIAGONIS	4169
ECHIICHTHYS VIPERA	2632
SCYLIORHINUS CANICULA	2617
MERLUCCIOUS MERLUCCIOUS	2305
POLLACHIUS VIRENS	2146
MICROMESISTIUS POUTASSOU	1583
AMMODYTES SPP	1389
TRISOPTERUS MINUTUS	1270
LOPHIUS PISCATORIUS	1202
PLATICHTHYS FLESUS	1154

Table 5: Most Frequently Mentioned Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

targetTaxonName	count
EMPTY	35805
AMMODYTES SPP	11880
OSTEICHTHYS - TELEOSTEI	11751
PSEUDOCALANUS ELONGATUS (FEMALE)	7076
DIGESTED REMAINS	6650
POLYCHAETA	6279
THYSANOESSA INERMIS	5748

targetTaxonName	count
CRUSTACEA	5627
COPEPODA-CALANOIDA	4629
COPEPODA (COPEPODITE 1-3)	4373
EUPHAUSIIDAE	4230
AMPHIPODA	3365
CRANGONIDAE	3337
CALANUS SPP	3174
OPHIURIDA (ORDER)	3138
COPEPODA (COPEPODITE 4-5)	2499
CRANGON CRANGON	2393
BRACHYURA-CANCRIDEA	2325
TEMORA SPP (MALE)	2309

Table 6: Most Frequent Interactions between Primary and Associate Taxa (up to 20 most frequent)

sourceTaxonName	interactionTypeName	targetTaxonName	count
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	EMPTY	9732
GADUS MORHUA	eats	EMPTY	6516
GADUS MORHUA	eats	THYSANOESSA INERMIS	5483
GADUS MORHUA	eats	OSTEICHTHYS - TELEOSTEI	5101
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	PSEUDOCALANUS ELONGATUS (FEMALE)	3908
MELANOGRAMMUS AEGLEFINUS	eats	AMMODYTES SPP	3741
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	COPEPODA (COPEPODITE 1-3)	3196
GADUS MORHUA	eats	PSEUDOCALANUS ELONGATUS (FEMALE)	3168
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	AMMODYTES SPP	2832
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	OSTEICHTHYS - TELEOSTEI	2696
GADUS MORHUA	eats	AMMODYTES SPP	2617

sourceTaxonName	interactionType	targetTaxonName	count
PLEURONECTES PLATESSA	eats	EMPTY	2385
EUTRIGLA GURNARDUS	eats	EMPTY	2309
MELANOGRAMMUS	eats	OPHIURIDA (ORDER)	2148
AEGLEFINUS MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	COPEPODA (COPEPODITE 4-5)	1899
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	TEMORA SPP (FEMALE)	1795
LEPIDORHOMBUS WHIFFIAGONIS	eats	EMPTY	1735
MERLANGIUS MERLANGUS	eats	TEMORA SPP (MALE)	1672
GADUS MORHUA	eats	NEPHROPS NORVEGICUS	1624

Interaction Networks

The figures below provide a graph view on the dataset under review. The first shows a summary network on the kingdom level, and the second shows how interactions on the family level. It is important to note that both network graphs were first aligned taxonomically using the Catalogue of Life. Please refer to the original (or verbatim) taxonomic names for a more original view on the interaction data.

Figure 3: Interactions on taxonomic kingdom rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life [download svg](#)

Figure 4: Interactions on the taxonomic family rank as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life. [download svg](#)

You can download the indexed dataset under review at [indexed-interactions.csv.gz](#). A tab-separated file can be found at [indexed-interactions.tsv.gz](#)

Geospatial Distribution

If geospatial information was extracted from the dataset under review, the map below will show their distribution. These maps were generated using MapServer

(McKenna et al. 2025) tools configured via map configuration indexed-interactions.map :

```
MAP
  SIZE 1600 800
  EXTENT -180 -90 180 90
  PROJECTION
    "init=epsg:4326"
  END
  LAYER # MODIS WMS map from NASA
    NAME "modis_nasa"
    TYPE RASTER
    OFFSITE 0 0 0
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE WMS
    CONNECTION "https://gibs.earthdata.nasa.gov/wms/epsg4326/best/wms.cgi?"

  METADATA
    "wms_srs" "EPSG:4326"
    "wms_name" "OSM_Land_Water_Map"
    "wms_server_version" "1.1.1"
    "wms_format" "image/jpeg"
  END
  CLASS
    STYLE
      COLOR 232 232 232
      OUTLINECOLOR 32 32 32
    END
  END
  END
  LAYER
    NAME "indexed-interactions"
    TYPE POLYGON
    STATUS ON
    CONNECTIONTYPE OGR
    CONNECTION "indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg"
    DATA "indexed-interactions-h3"
    CLASS
      STYLE
        COLORRANGE 253.0 231.0 37.0 32.0 164.0 134.0
        DATARANGE NULL NULL
        RANGEITEM "log_number_of_records"
        OUTLINECOLOR 0 0 0
      END
    END
  END
  END
```

END

Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Figure 5: Hexagonal grid cells indicate that interactions claims are available for selected geospatial area: light yellow means relatively fewer claims, dark green relatively more claims.

Associated data can be found in the geopackage files at indexed-interactions.gpkg for point data and indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg for data clustered in geospatial h3 hexagonals.

Learn more about the structure of this download at GloBI website, by opening a GitHub issue, or by sending an email.

Another way to discover the dataset under review is by searching for it on the GloBI website.

Taxonomic Alignment

As part of the review, all names are aligned against various name catalogs (e.g., col, ncbi, discoverlife, gbif, itis, wfo, mdd, tpt, pbdb, and worms). These alignments can help review name usage or aid in selecting of a suitable taxonomic name resource.

Table 7: Sample of Name Alignments

providedName	relationName	resolvedCatalogName	resolvedName
Abietinaria abietina	HAS_ACCEPTED	NAME	Abietinaria abietina
Abludomelita obtusata	HAS_ACCEPTED	NAME	Abludomelita obtusata
Abra alba	HAS_ACCEPTED	NAME	Abra alba
Abramis brama	HAS_ACCEPTED	NAME	Abramis brama

Table 8: Distribution of Taxonomic Ranks of Aligned Names by Catalog. Names that were not aligned with a catalog are counted as NAs. So, the total number of unaligned names for a catalog will be listed in their NA row.

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	NA	106
col	class	27

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
col	family	124
col	form	1
col	genus	191
col	gigaclass	1
col	infraclass	1
col	infraorder	2
col	infraphylum	2
col	kingdom	1
col	order	16
col	parvphylum	1
col	phylum	11
col	species	807
col	subclass	2
col	subfamily	7
col	subgenus	10
col	suborder	1
col	subphylum	1
col	subspecies	23
col	superfamily	1
col	superorder	1
col	tribe	5
col	variety	1
discoverlife	NA	1291
gbif	NA	117
gbif	class	25
gbif	family	124
gbif	genus	201
gbif	kingdom	1
gbif	order	16
gbif	phylum	12
gbif	species	813
gbif	subspecies	6
itis	NA	122
itis	class	23
itis	division	1
itis	family	120
itis	form	1
itis	genus	180
itis	infrakingdom	1
itis	infraorder	2
itis	infraphylum	1
itis	kingdom	1
itis	order	18
itis	phylum	9

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
itis	species	789
itis	subclass	7
itis	subfamily	4
itis	suborder	4
itis	subphylum	2
itis	subspecies	2
itis	superclass	1
itis	superfamily	1
itis	superorder	5
mdd	NA	1290
ncbi	NA	256
ncbi	clade	1
ncbi	class	24
ncbi	cohort	1
ncbi	family	120
ncbi	genus	174
ncbi	infraorder	3
ncbi	order	17
ncbi	phylum	11
ncbi	series	1
ncbi	species	673
ncbi	subclass	5
ncbi	subfamily	3
ncbi	subgenus	2
ncbi	suborder	3
ncbi	subphylum	1
ncbi	superclass	1
ncbi	superorder	3
pdb	NA	845
pdb	class	26
pdb	family	109
pdb	genus	101
pdb	infraclass	1
pdb	infraorder	2
pdb	kingdom	1
pdb	order	19
pdb	phylum	11
pdb	species	157
pdb	subclass	5
pdb	subfamily	7
pdb	suborder	4
pdb	subspecies	1
pdb	superclass	2
pdb	superfamily	1

resolvedCatalogName	resolvedRank	count
pbdb	superorder	3
pbdb	superphylum	1
pbdb	unranked clade	7
tpt	NA	1282
tpt	species	8
wfo	NA	1273
wfo	genus	16
wfo	species	1
worms	NA	167
worms	class	24
worms	family	113
worms	forma	1
worms	genus	164
worms	gigaclass	1
worms	infraclass	1
worms	infraorder	3
worms	infraphylum	2
worms	kingdom	1
worms	order	16
worms	parvphylum	1
worms	phylum	10
worms	phylum (division)	1
worms	species	769
worms	subclass	4
worms	subfamily	1
worms	suborder	3
worms	subphylum	2
worms	subspecies	7
worms	superfamily	1
worms	superorder	3

Table 9: Name relationship types per catalog. Name relationship type “NONE” means that a name was not recognized by the associated catalog. “SAME_AS” indicates either a “HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME” or “SYNONYM_OF” name relationship type. We recognize that “SYNONYM_OF” encompasses many types of nomenclatural synonymies (ICZN 1999) (e.g., junior synonym, senior synonyms).

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1207
col	SYNONYM_OF	486

resolvedCatalogName	relationName	count
col	NONE	113
discoverlife	NONE	1356
gbif	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1235
gbif	SYNONYM_OF	331
gbif	NONE	125
itis	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1154
itis	SYNONYM_OF	103
itis	NONE	129
mdd	NONE	1350
mdd	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1
ncbi	SAME_AS	1039
ncbi	NONE	267
ncbi	SYNONYM_OF	67
pbdb	NONE	872
pbdb	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	463
pbdb	SYNONYM_OF	74
tpt	NONE	1343
tpt	SYNONYM_OF	1
tpt	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7
wfo	NONE	1332
wfo	SYNONYM_OF	10
wfo	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	7
wfo	HAS_UNCHECKED_NAME	2
worms	HAS_ACCEPTED_NAME	1049
worms	SYNONYM_OF	201
worms	NONE	173

Table 10: List of Available Name Alignment Reports

catalog name	alignment results
col	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
ncbi	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
discoverlife	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
gbif	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
itis	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
wfo	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

catalog name	alignment results
mdd	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
tpt	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
pbdb	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)
worms	associated names alignments report in gzipped html, csv, and tsv)

Additional Reviews

Elton, Nomer, and other tools may have difficulties interpreting existing species interaction datasets. Or, they may misbehave, or otherwise show unexpected behavior. As part of the review process, detailed review notes are kept that document possibly misbehaving, or confused, review bots. An sample of review notes associated with this review can be found below.

Table 11: First few lines in the review notes.

reviewDate	reviewCommentType	reviewComment
2026-06-08T08:20:18Z	summary	https://zenodo.org/records/258222/files/millirse/Dapsi-integrated-database-and-portal-for-fish-stomach-records-v1.0.zip
2026-06-08T08:20:18Z	summary	225564 interaction(s)
2026-06-08T08:20:18Z	summary	0 note(s)
2026-06-08T08:20:18Z	summary	225564 info(s)

In addition, you can find the most frequently occurring notes in the table below.

: Most frequently occurring review notes, if any.

For additional information on review notes, please have a look at the first 500 Review Notes in html format or the download full gzipped csv or tsv archives.

GloBI Review Badge

As part of the review, a review badge is generated. This review badge can be included in webpages to indicate the review status of the dataset under review.

³Up-to-date status of the GloBI Review Badge can be retrieved from the GloBI Review Depot

Figure 6: Picture of a GloBI Review Badge ³

Note that if the badge is green, no review notes were generated. If the badge is yellow, the review bots may need some help with interpreting the species interaction data.

GloBI Index Badge

If the dataset under review has been registered with GloBI, and has been successfully indexed by GloBI, the GloBI Index Status Badge will turn green. This means that the dataset under review was indexed by GloBI and is available through GloBI services and derived data products.

Figure 7: Picture of a GloBI Index Badge ⁴

If you'd like to keep track of reviews or index status of the dataset under review, please visit GloBI's dataset index ⁵ for badge examples.

Discussion

This review and archive provides a means of creating citable versions of datasets that change frequently. This may be useful for dataset managers, including natural history collection data managers, as a backup archive of a shared Darwin Core archive. It also serves as a means of creating a trackable citation for the dataset in an automated way, while also including some information about the contents of the dataset.

This review aims to provide a perspective on the dataset to aid in understanding of species interaction claims discovered. However, it is important to note that this review does *not* assess the quality of the dataset. Instead, it serves as an indication of the open-ness⁶ and FAIRness (Wilkinson et al. 2016; Trekels et al. 2023) of the dataset: to perform this review, the data was likely openly available, **F**indable, **A**ccessible, **I**nteroperable and **R**eusable. The current Open-FAIR assessment is qualitative, and a more quantitative approach can be implemented with specified measurement units.

⁴Up-to-date status of the GloBI Index Badge can be retrieved from GloBI's API

⁵At time of writing (2026-06-08) the version of the GloBI dataset index was available at <https://globalbioticinteractions.org/datasets>

⁶According to <http://opendefinition.org/>: "Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone - subject only, at most, to the requirement to attribute and sharealike."

This report also showcases the reuse of machine-actionable (meta)data, something highly recommended by the FAIR Data Principles (Wilkinson et al. 2016). Making (meta)data machine-actionable enables more precise processing by computers, enabling even naive review bots like Nomer and Elton to interpret the data effectively. This capability is crucial for not just automating the generation of reports, but also for facilitating seamless data exchanges, promoting interoperability.

Acknowledgements

We thank the many humans that created us and those who created and maintained the data, software and other intellectual resources that were used for producing this review. In addition, we are grateful for the natural resources providing the basis for these human and bot activities. Also, thanks to <https://github.com/zygoballus> for helping improve the layout of the review tables.

Author contributions

Nomer was responsible for name alignments. Elton carried out dataset extraction, and generated the review notes. Preston tracked, versioned, and packaged, the dataset under review.

Appendix A. Review Files

The following files are produced in this review:

filename	description
biblio.bib	list of bibliographic reference of this review
check-dataset.sh	data review workflow/process as expressed in a bash script
data.zip	a versioned archive of the data under review
HEAD	the digital signature of the data under review
index.docx	review in MS Word format
index.html	review in HTML format
index.md	review in Pandoc markdown format
index.pdf	review in PDF format

filename	description
indexed-citations.csv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped comma-separated values file format
indexed-citations.html.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interactions claims in gzipped html file format
indexed-citations.tsv.gz	list of distinct reference citations for reviewed species interaction claims in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions-col-family-col-family.svg	network diagram showing the taxon family to taxon family interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions-col-kingdom-col-kingdom.svg	network diagram showing the taxon kingdom to taxon kingdom interaction claims in the dataset under review as interpreted by the Catalogue of Life via Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024)
indexed-interactions.csv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions.html.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-interactions.tsv.gz	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-interactions.parquet	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-interactions.png	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review plotted on a map
indexed-interactions.map	mapserver configuration to plot species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review on a map

filename	description
indexed-interactions.gpkg	species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-h3.gpkg	geospatially clustered h3 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in GeoPackage format
indexed-interactions-sample.csv	list of species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-interactions-sample.html	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in html format
indexed-interactions-sample.tsv	first 500 species interaction claims indexed from the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
indexed-names.csv.gz	taxonomic names indexed from the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped html format
indexed-names.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-col.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-col.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-col.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Catalogue of Life as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-discoverlife.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Discover Life bee species checklist as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-gbif.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with GBIF Backbone Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-itis.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-itis.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Integrated Taxonomic Information System (ITIS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-mdd.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Mammal Diversity Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-ncbi.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the NCBI Taxonomy as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-pbdb.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with Paleobiology Database as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-tpt.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the Terrestrial Parasite Tracker (TPT) Taxonomic Resource as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-wfo.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World of Flora Online as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.csv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped comma-separated values format

filename	description
indexed-names-resolved-worms.html.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped html format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.tsv.gz	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in gzipped tab-separated values format
indexed-names-resolved-worms.parquet	taxonomic names found in the dataset under review aligned with the World Register of Marine Species (WoRMS) as accessed through the Nomer Corpus of Taxonomic Resources (J. H. (ed.). Poelen 2024) in Apache Parquet format
indexed-names-sample.csv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
indexed-names-sample.html	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in html format
indexed-names-sample.tsv	first 500 taxonomic names found in the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
interaction.svg	diagram summarizing the data model used to index species interaction claims
nanopub-sample.trig	first 500 species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
nanopub.trig.gz	species interaction claims as expressed in the nanopub format (Kuhn and Dumontier 2014)
process.svg	diagram summarizing the data review processing workflow
prov.nq	origin of the dataset under review as expressed in rdf/nquads

filename	description
review.csv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped comma-separated values format
review.html.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped html format
review.tsv.gz	review notes associated with the dataset under review in gzipped tab-separated values format
review-sample.csv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in comma-separated values format
review-sample.html	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in html format
review-sample.tsv	first 500 review notes associated with the dataset under review in tab-separated values format
review.svg	a review badge generated as part of the dataset review process
zenodo.json	metadata of this review expressed in Zenodo record metadata

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